

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

Based on the requirements obtained from the assessment of observational data from the Tropical Atlantic, high-frequency output of selected variables will be provided for specific analyses to be compared in observations and simulations.

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WP6

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1 Executive summary

NextGEMS task 6.5 carried out dedicated sensitivity experiments with the two ocean models used in NextGEMS (ICON-O and FESOM). This report describes technical details of the model set-ups and the handling of high-frequency data for analyses of mixed-layer processes in the Tropical Atlantic. We provide high-frequency model output used in Task 6.5 for testing different vertical mixing schemes and associated parameter settings. This 3-hourly model output is made publicly available for a selected subdomain of particular interest: the tropical Atlantic, where many observations are available to validate the models. The entire high-frequency tropical Atlantic output from the upper 200m on a $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ latitude-longitude grid is published at the World Data Center for Climate (WDCC), in a long-term tape archive, where it is available under a CC BY 4.0 license (https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_WP6oc). Because the WDCC tape archive has a large latency and data retrieval is thus slow, we additionally provide a subset of the tropical Atlantic output on Zenodo, where data access is fast but data size is limited. For the latter dataset, time series from the models are provided for selected locations where observational data are available during the modelled time period (January 2014 - December 2015), also under a CC BY 4.0 license (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8225706>).

2 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
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To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks; | no |
| (ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing; | no |
| (iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes; | yes |
| (iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extratropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking; | no |
| (v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and | no |
| (vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take. | no |

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP6	Relevance in this deliverable?
To identify and evaluate key ocean and marine atmosphere features in the SR-ESM simulations of all three development cycles. (O1)	yes
To validate the marine planetary boundary layer representation of the SR-ESM simulations. (O1)	no
To provide ocean initial conditions for the coupled SR-ESM simulations. (O1)	yes
To provide developments towards an ocean mixed layer scheme adequate for SR-ESMs. (O1)	yes
To create numerical tools that generate output streams useful to the planetary boundary layer, ocean mixed-layer and fisheries communities. (O1,O3)	yes

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

As part of Task 6.5, we carried out a number of ocean-only sensitivity experiments with FESOM and ICON-O. The runs differ in their vertical mixing scheme and its parameter settings. In most of the experiments, the same mixing scheme and the same settings were used in FESOM and ICON. We then compared the different runs to each other as well as to observations, to find the best settings for the coupled nextGEMS configurations. In the report on Deliverable 6.5 and in the related publication (Bastin et al., 2024), the results of these analyses are described in detail. Here, we provide a technical description of how we saved the relevant data for the analyses and how we made high-frequency output of the model runs publicly available, for a selected subdomain of particular interest, i.e. the tropical Atlantic.

3.1 Model experiments

The model versions used in this study are compatible with the ones used in nextGEMS cycle 3. The FESOM model is documented in Danilov et al. (2017); Scholz et al. (2019, 2022), and ICON-O in Korn et al. (2022). All model runs were done at approximately 10km horizontal resolution in the domain of interest (ICON-O: globally, FESOM: tropical Atlantic, otherwise coarser). This is slightly coarser than the coupled nextGEMS runs, but in order to do so many sensitivity runs and not overstretch our computing resources, 10km was the finest resolution that was feasible. We did test runs with 40km and 5km resolution as well, and the change e.g. in mean tropical Atlantic mixed layer depth between 40 and 10km was much more substantial than between 10 and 5km. This suggested to us that doing the ocean vertical mixing sensitivity study at 10km resolution for the 5km nextGEMS coupled runs was reasonable.

3.2 FESOM

FESOM2 is a global unstructured-mesh ocean model developed at the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI) in Bremerhaven (Danilov et al., 2017). It is formulated on a triangular mesh, utilizes a finite-volume dynamical core and Arbitrary Lagrangian–Eulerian (ALE) vertical coordinates (Scholz et al., 2019). The model’s unstructured nature enables different types of local mesh refinements (e.g. one that follows local sea surface height variability). For this study we use a FESOM2 mesh that has 50 km resolution over most of the globe, except for the equatorial Atlantic, where it is set to 13 km resolution. FESOM uses a z^* vertical coordinate, where the total change in SSH is distributed equally over all layers, except the layer that touches the bottom.

3.3 ICON-O

ICON-O (Korn et al., 2022) is the ocean component of the **I**cosahedral **N**onhydrostatic Weather and Climate Model (ICON) in its Earth System Model configuration. It is developed at the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M) in Hamburg. The ocean component of ICON-ESM, ICON-O, solves the hydrostatic (the “Nonhydrostatic” in the name only refers to the atmospheric component) Boussinesq equations with a free surface. These equations are solved on a triangular horizontal grid, which is generated by dividing the spherical domain into an icosahedron

and subsequent division of the 12 icosahedron parts into triangles. In this study, an ICON grid with globally approximately uniform horizontal resolution of about 10km is used. While the ICON and FESOM horizontal grids are different, we argue that the two models are comparable, as we only compare results from our region of interest, i.e. the tropical Atlantic. In the vertical, a z^* coordinate is used where model levels follow the free surface. For details on the numerics or other specifics about ICON-O, see Korn et al. (2022).

3.4 Common settings and experiment descriptions

To meet the specific demands for Task 6.5, we decided on settings that would be shared by both models. Although we tried to homogenise the model settings between FESOM and ICON-O that are directly connected to the representation of vertical mixing, we left the rest of the model settings as they are commonly used in the FESOM and ICON-O communities at our institutes, i.e. partly different between the two models. This is intended and part of the reason why we do this study, to see how much of the variation between the different vertical mixing settings is model specific and how much happens similarly in both models.

We implemented a common vertical axis with 128 vertical levels for both models, with thicknesses ranging from 2 m near the surface to about 200 m near the seafloor. We also agreed to use the same vertical mixing schemes (TKE and KPP), as well as the same parameter settings. To make sure that our implementations of the TKE and KPP schemes are comparable, we use the versions provided by the CVMix (Community ocean Vertical Mixing) project, which has developed a library of standardised vertical mixing parameterisations to be used in ocean models. In the TKE scheme, we vary the c_k parameter (see table 3). For the KPP scheme, we run the models once with the default setting of $Ri_{crit} = 0.3$, and once with a reduced value of $Ri_{crit} = 0.27$. We do this because the best value for the critical bulk Richardson number is resolution dependent (e.g. Large et al., 1994). The resolution dependence follows from the bulk Richardson number being an approximation of the exact gradient Richardson number due to the finite thickness of the model levels. As the thickness decreases, the bulk Richardson number converges on the gradient Richardson number. Similarly, the critical bulk Richardson number chosen should converge on the critical gradient Richardson number of 0.25 with decreasing thickness. All model runs with their parameter settings are listed in Table 3.

We force all model runs with hourly ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020), and run them from the end of the 5-year spinup with adjusted mixing parameter settings for two years (2014 and 2015). Of these, we analyse only the second year when the upper ocean has sufficiently adjusted to the changed mixing settings. The year 2015 was chosen because a particularly strong Near-Inertial Wave (NIW) mixing event occurred in that year and was observed during a RV Meteor cruise in the tropical North Atlantic, as described and analysed by Hummels et al. (2020). We compare this unique set of observations against our models to assess whether they can reproduce deep reaching NIW mixing events like the one in 2015.

One notable difference between ICON-O and FESOM is the parameterisation of the surface fluxes, for which different bulk formulae are used for the ERA5 forcing. To investigate the effect of the bulk formulae, we did an additional run with ICON-O using the standard FESOM bulk formulae. The default bulk formulae in ICON-O for the ERA5 forcing are those of Kara et al. (2002) over ocean and sea ice, with water vapor pressure and 2 m specific humidity calculated using the (modified) equations from Buck (1981) and longwave radiation calculated using Berliand (1952). FESOM instead uses bulk formulae calculated according to Large and Yeager (2009) over the ocean and with constant bulk exchange coefficients over sea ice, as described in Tsu-

[Tsuji et al. \(2018\)](#). These are also implemented in ICON-O, but usually only used together with JRA55-do forcing ([Tsuji et al., 2018](#)).

The model runs were started on 1 January 2014, and run until 31 December 2015. This time period was chosen because of strong Near-Inertial-Wave (NIW) mixing events that were observed in 2015 (e.g. [Hummels et al., 2020](#)), and that we wanted to use for comparison and to assess the different mixing schemes' and models' ability to represent the turbulent mixing caused by strong NIWs. The results of this analysis have been submitted to JGR Oceans ([Mrozowska et al., subm.](#)).

All model runs were forced with hourly ERA5 data ([Hersbach et al., 2020](#)). However, the bulk formulae that are by default used in FESOM and ICON-O together with ERA5 forcing are different. In ICON-O, the formulae from [Kara et al. \(2002\)](#) are used over ocean and sea ice, with the calculation of water vapour pressure and specific humidity following [Buck \(1981\)](#) and the longwave radiation being calculated as in [Berliand \(1952\)](#). In FESOM, bulk formulae from [Large and Yeager \(2009\)](#) are used over the ocean and from [Tsuji et al. \(2018\)](#) over sea ice.

All variables are available at 3-hourly intervals, to enable comparison to high-frequency observational data for the analysis of short-term processes, such as the diurnal cycle or near-inertial waves. The output variables that we provide include temperature, salinity, density, velocities, shear, buoyancy frequency, Richardson Number, turbulent kinetic energy, vertical diffusivity and viscosity (3D for the upper 200m), as well as 2D fields like surface fluxes (heat, momentum, freshwater) and mixed layer depth.

A list of the model runs from which tropical Atlantic high-frequency output is available is given in Table 3.

The two vertical mixing schemes that we tested are two of the most widely used vertical mixing schemes in global ocean models. Both of them are based on the classical eddy diffusivity concept, parameterising the small-scale vertical turbulent fluxes of a variable as the product of a coefficient called eddy diffusivity and the large-scale vertical gradient of the variable in question. In the TKE (turbulent kinetic energy) scheme ([Gaspar et al., 1990](#)), the eddy diffusivity is determined as a function of the turbulent kinetic energy, for which an additional prognostic equation is included in the model. In the KPP (K-profile parameterisation) scheme ([Large et al., 1994](#)), the eddy diffusivity is instead given as a specified vertical profile in the surface ocean boundary layer. The boundary layer depth is determined as the depth below which the bulk Richardson Number becomes larger than a critical value Ri_{crit} . Ri_{crit} is usually set to 0.3 but should ideally approach the critical gradient Richardson Number of 0.25 with increasingly fine vertical resolution. For KPP, we vary the value of Ri_{crit} in the sensitivity runs. For TKE, we vary the value of the c_k parameter (cf. [Gaspar et al., 1990](#), Equation 10).

Additionally, we did a number of runs only with ICON-O, changing different aspects of the TKE scheme. One of these has an extension of the TKE scheme: the parameterisation of Langmuir turbulence ([Axell, 2002](#)). Langmuir turbulence, which is generated through the interaction of wind-driven surface currents and wind-generated surface waves, is responsible for additional turbulent energy input into the upper ocean, and it has been shown to be important over much of the global ocean area (e.g. [Belcher et al., 2012](#)). Since we do not simulate surface waves with ICON-O, the effect of the Langmuir turbulence is missing if it is not parameterised. Two runs were done with increased minimum background vertical mixing, one by increasing the minimum background TKE from 10^{-6} J/kg to 10^{-5} J/kg (in this case the diffusivity and viscosity are then still dependent on the stability of the water column), and one by setting a minimum background value directly for the vertical diffusivity (10^{-5} m²/s) and viscosity (10^{-4} m²/s) as it is also done

Table 3: Overview of ocean-only model runs

Name	Model	Mixing scheme	Parameter settings
F_TKE_01	FESOM	TKE	$c_k = 0.1$
F_TKE_02	FESOM	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$
F_TKE_03	FESOM	TKE	$c_k = 0.3$
F_KPP_030	FESOM	KPP	$Ri_{crit} = 0.3$
F_KPP_027	FESOM	KPP	$Ri_{crit} = 0.27$
I_TKE_01	ICON-O	TKE	$c_k = 0.1$
I_TKE_02	ICON-O	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$
I_TKE_03	ICON-O	TKE	$c_k = 0.3$
I_KPP_030	ICON-O	KPP	$Ri_{crit} = 0.3$
I_KPP_027	ICON-O	KPP	$Ri_{crit} = 0.27$
I_TKE_02_Langmuir	ICON-O	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$, additional Langmuir parameterisation
I_TKE_02_minTKE	ICON-O	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$, minimum background TKE = 10^{-5} J/kg (default: 10^{-6} J/kg)
I_TKE_02_minKv	ICON-O	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$, minimum background diffusivity = 10^{-5} m ² /s (viscosity = 10^{-4} m ² /s)
I_TKE_02_ncarbf	ICON-O	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$, FESOM default bulk formulae

in the KPP scheme. The last run was done to check the effect of the different sets of default forcing bulk formulae that are used in ICON-O and FESOM with ERA5 forcing. For this, we ran ICON-O with the same settings as in the ICON_TKE_02 run, except that we used the same bulk formulae that are by default used in FESOM.

3.5 Data selection and publication

The subdomain that we chose for analysis and data publication is the tropical Atlantic, as proposed in the nextGEMS Grant Agreement. There are a number of reasons for this: The tropics are especially important for the global circulation and climate, but at the same time many of the large model biases are located there. Tuning the model to get an improved tropical upper ocean representation could thus benefit the simulation of the global climate. The tropical Atlantic in particular is of scientific interest to several of the PIs of Work Package 6. Additionally, there are quite a number of available observations from the tropical Atlantic (e.g. from the well-maintained PIRATA/“Prediction and Research Moored Array in the Tropical Atlantic” program)

which we need to validate the models.

For the study to be published in GMD, we agreed on a number of common analyses, which dictated the demands for output, both in terms of variables selected and frequency of output. The analyses of the diurnal cycle and near-inertial waves called for high-frequency output and we decided to store 3-hourly data.

Both FESOM and ICON run on triangular grids, though different ones. For easier analysis and comparability between the two models, and to ensure accessibility for users unexperienced with unstructured grids, we regridded the data from both models to a $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ longitude-latitude grid for the tropical Atlantic domain ($10^\circ\text{S} - 30^\circ\text{N}$, $60^\circ\text{W} - 15^\circ\text{E}$).

We decided to publish the model output in the World Data Center for Climate (WDCC, <https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/>) of the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ). The WDCC is a long-term archive for large datasets which are relevant for Earth System research. There is already a nextGEMS data project in the WDCC (<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/project?acronym=nextGEMS>), in which e.g. parts of the Cycle 2 coupled model output have been published. We decided to publish our ocean-only sensitivity runs under the same data project.

Although the WDCC provides a good opportunity to publish large datasets because it is a tape archive, this also means that it has a large latency and that users will therefore have to endure long waiting times to retrieve data. We therefore additionally provide a much smaller subset of the tropical Atlantic model output on Zenodo which is a faster platform but can only handle limited amounts of data. This subset was chosen to include specific points where observations are available in the modelled time period (more details below).

To connect our experiment suite to the nextGEMS cycle simulation and to provide a single reference for users with interest in using the data for further studies on ocean mixing, we included the information given here in the [easy.gems](https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/ocean_only.html#ocean-sim) website:

https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/ocean_only.html#ocean-sim

3.5.1 WDCC: entire tropical Atlantic

In the WDCC, we published the output from the tropical Atlantic from all FESOM and ICON-O model runs listed in Table 3. The published output is 3-hourly, from the upper 200m, and on a $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ grid. It can be found here: https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_WP6oc (Bastin et al., 2023b).

3.5.2 Zenodo: selected time series

We provide selected time series of the model output at locations where observational data is available during the modelled time period:

- PIRATA buoys with high-frequency observations of hydrographic parameters and storms passing in 2014/2015 which are also used for an in-depth analysis of the representation of Near-Inertial Waves in the different model runs in (Mrozowska et al., *subm.*) (<https://www.pmel.noaa.gov/tao/drupal/disdell/>):

– 11.5N, 23W

- 15N, 38W
- PIRATA buoys with microstructure measurements (i.e. turbulence measurements which can be compared to the turbulent mixing in the models, <https://www.pmel.noaa.gov/tao/drupal/chipod/>):
- At the same locations: Moorings with publicly available measurements of the subsurface flow field (<https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.923605>):
 - 0N, 23W
 - 0N, 10W
- Moorings with high-frequency measurements of hydrographic parameters:
 - 11.0N, 21.2W (<https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.924270>, <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.924266>)
 - 17.6N, 24.3W (<https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.908822>, <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.924249>)

The published time series from the ICON-O and FESOM model runs can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8225706> (Bastin et al., 2023a).

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5 Dissemination and uptake

5.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

5.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

We have published the entire tropical Atlantic high-frequency data in the World Data Centre for Climate (WDCC) of the German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ). It is publicly available there under a CC BY 4.0 license, which makes it theoretically accessible to anyone. However, due to the amount of data and the relatively high latency of the WDCC (which is a tape archive), members of the general public without access to a supercomputer might face technical difficulties in obtaining the data. Therefore, we additionally selected a number of locations where observational time series are available (PIRATA buoys or long-term moorings) and published this much smaller subselection of data on Zenodo. The data access is then very fast and should be easily possible for anyone with an internet connection.

6 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

7 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Originally, we proposed to test a third vertical mixing scheme with ICON-O in addition to TKE and KPP: the $k - \epsilon$ scheme which evolved from the TKE scheme. This suggestion relied on technical work that was planned to be done in another, cooperating project (the TRR 181, <https://www.trr-energytransfers.de/>), because the $k - \epsilon$ scheme is not yet implemented in ICON-O. However, the implementation of the scheme in ICON-O in the TRR 181 proved more difficult

than anticipated, and it is still not running due to technical problems. We therefore decided to do an additional test run with an extension of the TKE scheme instead: the parameterisation of Langmuir turbulence (Axell, 2002), as described above. The run with additional Langmuir parameterisation (only ICON-O) is included in the published data sets.

Although we did run FESOM with different vertical (and horizontal) resolutions, as proposed in the nextGEMS Grant Agreement for Task 6.5, we decided not to publish these runs but instead do additional test runs with FESOM using the same high vertical resolution as ICON-O and testing the same vertical mixing schemes and parameters. These runs have been described here and included in the published dataset. Doing these coordinated sensitivity experiments with the two models instead of only ICON-O as proposed in the Grant Agreement enabled us to see which changes happen systematically due to changes in the mixing scheme parameters, and which are model dependent. For more details see the report on Deliverable 6.5.

8 Sustainability

8.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable (D6.4) describes how we made high-frequency model output of the ocean-only sensitivity experiments publicly available for a selected subdomain of particular interest, i.e. the tropical Atlantic. A more detailed description of the results of the vertical mixing sensitivity study can be found in the Deliverable 6.5 report which belongs to the same work package.

The ocean-only test runs with the different vertical mixing scheme settings served as a starting point for test runs with the coupled model, and for ICON finally led to changes in the vertical mixing settings from the coupled Cycle 2 to the Cycle 3 run (Work Package 2 "Model Validation and Development"). Although we found less impact of the vertical mixing settings on model biases than we expected, small improvements could be achieved in the coupled ICON run by changing the vertical mixing settings based on our findings from the ocean-only sensitivity runs. In particular, we had problems in the coupled Cycle 1 run with a large bias in the equatorial Atlantic zonal SST gradient and a large associated westerly trade wind bias. This was already improved slightly in the coupled Cycle 2 run by nudging the SST to reanalysis during the last year of the ocean spinup, but the problem still persisted. With the ocean-only vertical mixing sensitivity runs, we could show that the equatorial zonal SST gradient is (very slightly) improved when the c_k parameter in the TKE scheme is reduced to 0.1. Changing this in the coupled ICON model led to a further improvement in the coupled SST/trade wind bias in the tropical Atlantic in Cycle 3.

9 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022

- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid

10 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>